

Poisoning Object Detection Models for Surface Defect Inspection in Steel Manufacturing

Abstract—As Machine Learning (ML) becomes integral to automated quality assurance, the security of ML models emerges as a critical concern for manufacturing processes. Among the threats posed by adversarial machine learning attacks, *data poisoning* — the corruption of training data to introduce malicious behavior in ML models — represents the most concerning ML-related security risk to the industry [1].

This paper investigates the vulnerability of ML-based quality assurance systems to data poisoning attacks in manufacturing, with steel surface defect inspection as a use-case. Using a popular object detection model trained on an industrial steel manufacturing image dataset, we evaluate two data poisoning approaches: 1) *image poisoning* and 2) *label poisoning*, targeting three adversarial objectives: a) misclassification of defect criticality, b) erroneous size estimation, and c) missed defect detection. Our experiments show that label poisoning is a serious threat to the accuracy of steel defect inspection, potentially leading to significant misvaluation in defect size and defect criticality even when less than 12% of the training data is compromised. On the other hand, we show that image poisoning has little impact on the accuracy of steel defect inspection even when more than half of the samples in a class are poisoned.

I. INTRODUCTION

Machine learning (ML) is being increasingly used to automate manufacturing processes such as predictive maintenance, visual quality inspection or defect detection. This digital transformation provides higher productivity, increases efficiency, and reduces cost. However, when ML fails, it can lead to dire consequences, such as production downtime or wrong quality assessment.

Research in adversarial machine learning has shown that the behavior of ML systems can be manipulated by attackers [2]. Among adversarial ML attacks, *data poisoning* stands out because it corrupts the behavior of ML models by compromising their training data. Data poisoning impacts ML models early in their life cycle, embedding systematic malicious behaviors without requiring adversarial access when ML models are deployed and used in operations. Consequently, poisoning represents the most concerning security threats to applying ML in industrial applications [1], acknowledged by the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) for its criticality and lack of single foolproof mitigation approach to all poisoning scenarios [3]. While poisoning attacks have been thoroughly investigated in the image classification domain, there is no comprehensive study of poisoning against object detection models. Similarly, scenarios, data, and poisoning attack objectives relevant to ML-based manufacturing have not yet been addressed in this context.

The focus of this work is to assess the threat of poisoning attacks in steel manufacturing processes, where quality

assurance leverages ML-based analysis. The considered use case involves applying an object detection model to identify and classify surface defects on steel sheets — an illustrative example of vision-based machine learning. In this use case, it is essential to ensure that adversaries cannot compromise the quality assurance process and generate misleading quality assessments of the product. Such compromise could result in the use of defective steel in critical structures, failing to meet the required material properties, thereby undermining safety and reliability. Severe consequences can include structural failures in construction, bridge collapse, or road accidents due to premature fatigue of automotive frames.

In this paper, we study the vulnerability of ML-based steel defect detection to the two main data poisoning approaches: *image poisoning* and *label poisoning*. We evaluate the impact of the poisoned training data rate on the success of three adversarial objectives targeting steel quality metrics: a) the count of detected defects, b) the inferred defect sizes, and c) the criticality level of defects. (Sec. IV). We show that *image poisoning* hardly affects the accuracy of any steel quality metric, even when most of the training data is compromised (Sec. V). Consequently, image poisoning represents little security threat to ML-based steel quality assurance. On the other hand, label poisoning decreases the accuracy (*Recall* : 0.54 \rightarrow 0.31) of defect criticality detection and seriousness of detected defects (*Size* : 28kpx \rightarrow 13kpx) by poisoning only 11,6% of the training data. This demonstrates that label poisoning is a significant threat to ML-based steel quality assurance and we recommend solutions to mitigate it.

II. BACKGROUND & RELATED WORK

Data poisoning refers to the manipulation of ML models training data such that the model's behavior during inference is steered towards a chosen attacker's goals. *Availability attacks* aim to degrade the overall model accuracy, making the model practically unusable, while *integrity attacks* target specific misclassifications while the model's overall accuracy remaining seemingly unchanged. These types of attacks express the core of data poisoning. Carefully crafted patterns are injected into the ML model training data, resulting in malicious behavior during inference.

Data poisoning attacks are often discriminated based on whether they poison the input samples or the output labels of the model. This discrimination is important, since the adversary's capabilities to modify the sample or the label can be a key differentiator of the attack sensibility. This study focuses on object detection task where the aim is to identify surface defects from an image. The defects are labeled with

bounding boxes that depict the defect position, size, and category. Attacks that only modify the input sample (image) are referred to as *clean-label* while those that only modify the labels, i.e. object bounding boxes and their categories, are referred to as *clean-image*.

Backdoor attacks are a type of integrity attacks aiming to poison the model so that the targeted adversarial behavior is activated using a trigger during inference. A backdoor attack typically requires inserting a visible patch in the training images and manipulating the sample labels [4]. It also requires similar triggers to be present in the images during inference. Nevertheless, clean-image backdoor attacks also exist, triggered by naturally occurring patterns of objects in the image [5]. Such an attack does not require modifications to the image during training or inference.

Label flipping is a simple clean-image data poisoning technique in which the attacker changes the labels of training samples. Label flipping can achieve a high success rate in targeted misclassification by poisoning only, e.g., 2% of the optimally selected training data [6].

Feature collision attacks such as *Poison Frogs* [7] and *Bullseye Polytope* [8] are clean-label attacks that manipulate the features of training image samples with imperceptible perturbations, so the model learns to misclassify a target sample during inference. These attacks target only specific samples, while leaving the overall accuracy of the model unchanged. In object detection cases, Lee et Al. [9] demonstrate that a selected type of maritime vessel can be misclassified by poisoning 2% of the training data using the clean-label Poison Frog attack.

Bilevel optimization is a poisoning technique that optimizes two loss terms simultaneously, the training loss and the adversary loss. Training loss is the general performance of the model in its dedicated task, while adversary loss is misclassification of a specific target image. The bilevel optimization problem was solved first by using back-gradient descent to craft the poisoned samples [10] and the solution is extended to modern large models with *MetaPoison* [11] to misclassify specific samples and further *Witches Brew* [12] to reduce overall model test accuracy. *Adversarial poisoning* [13] is a more direct and efficient approach where the attacker uses adversarial examples [14] to poison training data. *MetaPoison* and *Witches' Brew* are clean-label attacks, while adversarial poisoning can use either clean-label or flipped-label variants.

While there is a large amount of research work regarding poisoning image classification, studies on poisoning object detection models are mostly limited to backdoor attacks [15], [16]. Existing approaches, derived from image classification studies, focus on misclassification and missed detections, while dismissing relevant adversarial objectives like targeting size and position of bounding boxes. Furthermore, the use cases and datasets considered in prior work have little relevance to manufacturing processes. Everyday object containing datasets CIFAR [17] and ImageNet [18] are most commonly used in computer vision literature and their characteristics differ significantly from images of industrial

processes, leaving a research gap. This paper addresses this gap by evaluating six different label poisoning and image poisoning attacks on a real-world manufacturing dataset and object detection model. We also include manufacturing relevant adversarial objectives such as bounding box size and position poisoning in our attacks.

III. POISONING QUALITY ASSURANCE IN STEEL MANUFACTURING

A. Automated quality assurance in steel manufacturing

Steel sheet is a fundamental product of the iron and steel industry, and its quality has a direct impact on both the performance of end products and the economic competitiveness of manufacturers. Surface defects, such as scratches, surface crazing, and rolled-in scale, are inevitable due to production constraints. Fig. 1 shows two steel sheet images with surface defects. These imperfections not only compromise the visual quality of the product, but also degrade essential material properties, including corrosion resistance, wear resistance, and fatigue strength, potentially resulting in significant financial losses. Consequently, accurate and real-time surface defect inspection has become a critical component of quality assurance in steel manufacturing. In recent years, online surface inspection of steel sheets has emerged as a crucial process and has been increasingly implemented using computer vision techniques. In general, defect detection and classification using these techniques involve identifying defective regions from large volumes of surface images and categorizing the detected defects.

Extensive research has addressed this issue, with the most common methods used to date range from classical statistical approaches (e.g., thresholding, clustering, edge detection) to spectral (e.g., Fourier, Gabor, wavelet transforms [20]) and model-based techniques (e.g., Markov random fields, Weibull models) [21]. More recent advances leverage machine learning, including supervised, unsupervised, and reinforcement learning. Although traditional methods are effective in controlled settings, their performance degrades under variable conditions such as lighting or surface texture. In contrast, machine learning models demonstrate greater adaptability and robustness by learning to generalize across changing environments.

B. Poisoning ML-based steel defect detection

Three quality metrics are used to assess the quality of steel sheets through visual inspection. These metrics quantify the count, size, and nature of defects in a given steel sheet as follows:

- **Defect count:** The number of defects in the steel sheet. A higher count implies a lower quality.
- **Defect size:** The area of steel affected by defects in the steel sheet. Larger area implies lower quality.
- **Defect category:** The severity of defects present in the steel sheet as an integer from 1 to 4, where 4 represents the most serious/critical defects and 1 the least. The presence of high category defects (3-4) implies a lower quality.

Fig. 1. Images from the Severstal Steel Defect Detection dataset [19] with highlighted defects. Top: sheet with class 1 defects. Bottom: sheet with a class 4 defect.

For our poisoning attacks, we define the adversary’s goal as causing the ML-based steel sheet quality assessment to *overestimate the good quality of a steel sheet*, which is equivalent to underestimating the criticality, count, or size of defects present in the steel sheet. This goal would result in low quality steel to be used for manufacturing instead of being discarded. The adversary aims to achieve its objective using a minimal number of poisoned samples. The following three adversarial objectives are targeted at each of the quality metrics, and each objective is implemented using two poisoning strategies.

- **Missed detection:** The adversary aims to miss defects, reducing the detected *defect count*. The objective is pursued by 1) disrupting the spatial alignment between image features and ground truth labels by randomly relocating defect bounding boxes — *label position manipulation*. 2) Removing the essential features from the image that causes the detection — *feature elimination*.
- **Erroneous size estimation:** The adversary aims to reduce the detected *defect size*. The objective is pursued by 1) reducing the dimension of the defect bounding boxes, encouraging the model to predict smaller defects — *label size manipulation*. 2) Replacing the defect features in the images with features of smaller defects of the same type — *feature compression*.
- **Misclassification of defect criticality:** The adversary aims to downplay the defect severity by inducing misclassification into lower *defect category*. The objective is pursued by 1) enforcing targeted misclassification of defect category by modifying the defect category in the training data labels. A severe defect category is flipped into least critical category (e.g., $4 \rightarrow 1$) — *label category flipping*. 2) Replacing the defect features of severe defects in the images with those of the least critical ones — *feature substitution*.

For each objective, the first strategy uses label poisoning (clean-image) while the second uses image poisoning (clean-label).

C. Adversarial capabilities

We limit the adversarial capabilities to manipulating a part of the whole training dataset prior to training. The adversary has no access to the model training process during training. The attacks are either clean-label image poisoning or clean-image label poisoning, representing scenarios where the adversary is capable of accessing only the images or their labels but not both at the same time. In all attacks, the poisoned samples are randomly selected from the whole training dataset, representing a case in which the attacker has access to only a fixed subset of data (which cannot be selected).

Label poisoning attacks are *black-box*, meaning they do not assume knowledge of the ML model. Labels are modified according to predefined rules.

Image poisoning attacks are *gray-box* in our setup. They do not require access to the targeted model to attack, but they require access to a surrogate model that the attacker can use to craft the poisons. As a surrogate model, we use the same architecture as the targeted model, as it is publicly available, and we train it with clean public data.

IV. EVALUATION SETUP

A. Data and model

We evaluate the vulnerability of the detection transformer (DETR) [22] object detection model to data poisoning attacks. The DETR model uses a transformer-based architecture with a convolutional neural network backbone. We use the pre-trained detr-resnet-50 model and fine-tune using the AdamW optimizer with an initial learning rate of 10^{-5} for the transformer and 10^{-6} for the backbone. A weight decay of 10^{-4} was applied and training was conducted for 200 epochs. The number of epochs was determined based on the progression of training and validation loss in the clean model. The same parameters were applied across all experiments. For each poisoning setting, training was repeated five times with different random selections of poisoned samples, and we report the average results from these repetitions.

Our experiments are based on the Severstal: Steel Defect Detection dataset hosted on Kaggle [19]. We conduct model training and evaluation on a subset of the publicly available dataset. Our dataset consists of 1000 training samples and 500 samples for model evaluation. The dataset samples are randomly selected with the aim of improving class balance across defect types. The label distribution is shown in Table I. While the original dataset provides segmented defects, we rely on their bounding boxes for the object detection use-case. Fig. 1 shows two samples from the dataset with highlighted labeled defects.

TABLE I

DISTRIBUTION OF DEFECT CRITICALITY CLASS IN TRAINING AND TEST DATA. NUMBER OF IMAGES CONTAINING EACH CRITICALITY CLASS (1-4) AND NO DEFECT ('NONE'). SOME SAMPLES CONTAIN MORE THAN ONE DEFECT CLASS.

Defect criticality class	Training	Testing
1	246	130
2	138	74
3	325	154
4	291	142
None	117	50
Total	1000	500

B. Poisoning attacks

We deploy the adversarial poisoning algorithm [13] to generate poisoned images. The paper demonstrates the use of the industry standard Projected Gradient Descent (PGD) [23] for adversarial poisoning. The PGD algorithm computes the loss term gradients for the model, back-propagates the loss gradients, and adds perturbations to the input image based on the calculated gradients. For the loss term calculation, the labels can be altered to cause the input image to express features that would lead to prediction with forward pass that aligns better with the modified labels. We replicate the adversarial poisoning algorithm [13] with 250 steps, as do the authors but we do not impose constraints on the perturbation magnitude for the image, as the original paper suggests that larger allowed perturbations are more effective. We use 0.1 step size after verifying that it generates adversarial examples that have successful misclassification from class 4 to class 1. Figure 2 shows the effect of the PGD attack on an image sample, which is not noticeable to the human eye.

Image poisoning and label poisoning attacks are performed against the three quality metrics individually, resulting in six attack strategies. The label poisoning attacks are:

- **Label class flipping (LC):** Class 4 defects are flipped to class 1.
- **Label position manipulation (LP):** The bounding boxes of class 4 defects are moved to a random position in the image.
- **Label size manipulation (LS):** The center position of the class 4 defect bounding boxes are maintained but the width and height of the boxes is halved.

The image poisoning attacks are

Fig. 2. Example class 4 defect. Original (top left), perturbed with PGD (top right), perturbation (bottom).

- **Feature substitution (IC):** PGD algorithm is used with manipulated defect classes. Class 4 defects are flipped to class 1.
- **Feature elimination (IP):** PGD algorithm is used with original labels, but the perturbation direction is ascending gradient, opposite of the normal descending.
- **Feature compression (IS):** PGD algorithm is used with manipulated bounding box sizes. The box width and height are halved.

In this paper, the poison rate is defined as the percentage of modified images that originally contain class 4 defects in the training data. We use poison rates of 20, 40, 60 and 80% of class 4 training samples, corresponding to 5.8, 11.6, 17.4, and 23.2% of the whole training dataset.

C. Evaluation metrics

To assess the impact of data poisoning on steel quality evaluation, we use five metrics.

Precision and **Recall** measure classification accuracy by comparing predicted objects to ground truth. This requires matched pairs based on an Intersection-over-Union (IoU) threshold and a minimum confidence score. For matched boxes, we require only a single pixel of overlap between predicted and ground truth bounding boxes to meet the IoU criterion, since exact box placement is not critical for any of the quality metrics in the application. Selecting the confidence threshold requires balancing between precision and recall scores. We choose to use class-specific confidence thresholds that maximize the F1-score on clean model predictions. The model prediction F1-score was evaluated over the range [0.01, 1] in steps of 0.01, and the confidence threshold resulting highest F1-score is selected. The resulting confidence score for classes 1 and 4 are 0.48 and 0.50, respectively.

Defect count measures the total number of predicted boxes above the confidence threshold, regardless of matching, providing insight into over- or under-detection effects introduced by poisoning.

Fig. 3. Evolution of steel quality metrics with poisoning rate across six data poisoning attacks. Precision (top left), Recall (top center), Bounding box size relative error (top right), Defect count (bottom left), and Defect size (bottom center).

Defect size is measured from the predicted bounding boxes from matched defects only. Bounding box size refers to the average bounding box size (in thousands of pixels, kpx) from the predictions.

Relative size error is calculated from the absolute values of the relative errors in bounding box sizes. Due to large outliers, we use the median of the relative errors for each random seed experiment.

V. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

We ran the six poisoning attacks introduced in Section IV-B against training data containing *class 4* defects (291 samples). The impact of these attacks on five evaluation metrics (for *class 4* defects) is depicted in Fig. 3 according to an increasing poisoning rate: 0-80% of *class 4* samples poisoned. Table II complements this figure showing detailed results for selected poisoning attacks, including also the impact of poisoning attacks on *class 1* defects accuracy (targeted by misclassification). Accuracy for other classes is not reported as they were not affected by the poisoning attacks.

Effectiveness of Label vs. Image poisoning strategies. Label poisoning attacks successfully decrease the accuracy of all steel quality metrics using an appropriate poisoning strategy. For instance, *label class flipping (LC)* drops the recall of *class 4* by 80% (.54 \rightarrow .11) with 60% poison

TABLE II

EVALUATION RESULTS FOR SELECTED POISONING ATTACK SETTINGS FOR CLASS 1 (LEFT) AND CLASS 4 (RIGHT). RED RESULTS INDICATE $> 20\%$ PERFORMANCE DEGRADATION FROM BASELINE.

Strategy	Precision		Recall		Size (kpx)		Size error	
	1	4	1	4	1	4	1	4
None	0.52	0.76	0.57	0.54	1.5	28	0.35	0.39
LS 20%	0.53	0.71	0.58	0.61	1.5	18	0.36	0.51
LP 40%	0.50	0.65	0.59	0.53	1.5	24	0.39	0.45
LS 40%	0.51	0.67	0.59	0.60	1.5	13	0.36	0.62
LC 40%	0.44	0.82	0.59	0.31	1.6	22	0.35	0.43
LC 60%	0.34	0.87	0.58	0.11	1.6	30	0.38	0.44
LP 60%	0.50	0.53	0.55	0.50	1.5	24	0.37	0.59
LS 60%	0.53	0.62	0.57	0.61	1.5	10	0.38	0.69

rate, and *label size manipulation (LS)* drops the detected size of defects by 53% (28kpx \rightarrow 13kpx) with 40% poison rate. On the other hand, image poisoning was unsuccessful at degrading the accuracy of any quality metric, even with high poisoning rates, which can be seen in Fig. 3 from the lack of change in any metric across increasing poison rate. The adversarial capabilities used in this work differ from other data poisoning works in object detection domain where [15] enable adversarial access during inference and [16] only targets specific instances of object class. Our more restrictive adversarial capabilities are the likely reason our results contrast with these works as well as prior work on

image classification, which demonstrated strong efficacy for misclassification at low poisoning budgets [13].

Impact of poisoning rate. The effectiveness of poisoning attacks increases with the poisoning rate. For label poisoning attacks, we can observe that the accuracy of quality metrics (Precision, Recall, Size error, etc.) degrades linearly as the poisoning rate increases. In controlled manufacturing environments, data pipelines are usually centralized and labeling processes are audited. While introducing a large fraction of poisoned samples may be challenging, if an adversary gains access to the data stream and can inject 11-23% of poisoned data (40-80% of class 4 in our experiments), data poisoning can have severe operational consequences.

Interactions between attack objectives and quality metrics. We can observe that poisoning attacks primarily affect the quality metric they target, without affecting any other quality metric. For instance, *label size manipulation (LS)* reduces detected size and increases size error without degrading precision or recall. This raises our attention to carefully monitoring and validating all steel quality metrics to detect a potential poisoning attack and mitigate its effect. On the other hand, *label class flipping (LC)* provides the expected decrease in *class 4* recall and have the logical side effect of decreasing *class 1* precision, as more *class 4* defects are misidentified as *class 1*.

To mitigate the label poisoning threat, industries implementing ML techniques for quality control should adopt strict data provenance management [24] by vetting data sources and focus on selecting trusted training data sources. Down the line, they must implement strict access control to the training data to prevent any label alteration after data collection. Technical mitigation against label flipping, such as label sanitization [25], should be employed to identify and correct incorrect labels in training data before using it for training. Finally, careful monitoring and validation of all quality metrics must be regularly performed to detect any degradation potentially associated with data poisoning and to enable timely remediation.

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